
Software prototype for routing and scheduling of delivery orders

Deliverable 2.4

Version 1.0

Project title:	Fostering sustainable consumer behaviour with inclusive bicycle logistics infrastructure in urban outskirts
Project acronym:	SuCoLo
Project duration:	01/2024 – 06/2026
Project number:	F-DUT-2022-0007
Work package/Task:	WP2 / T2.4
Project website:	https://sucolo.eu/
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This project has been funded by the Austrian Research Promotion Agency (FFG), Ministry of Enterprises and Made in Italy (MIMIT), the Federal Ministry of Research, Technology and Space in Germany (BMFTR) and the Swedish funding agency (Vinnova) under the Driving Urban Transitions Partnership, which has been co-funded by the European Union under grant agreement no. 905465.

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

**Bundesministerium
Klimaschutz, Umwelt,
Energie, Mobilität,
Innovation und Technologie**

Gefördert durch:

Document versions

Version	Date	Changes	Authors
V0.1	01.04.2025	Initial document	Benjamin Gaunitz
V0.2	08.08.2025	Review and formatting	Michael Thelen
V1.0	12.08.2025	Finalisation of the document	Michael Thelen, Olivia Zechner

List of abbreviations

API	Application Programming Interface
HTTPS	HyperText Transfer Protocol Secure
JWT	JSON Web Token
LDAP	Lightweight Directory Access Protocol
OSRM	Open Source Routing Machine
RBAC	Role-Based Access Control
REST	Representational State Transfer
SAML	Security Assertion Markup Language
TLS	Transport Layer Security
UI	User interface
VROOM	Vehicle Routing Open-source Optimization Machine
VRP	Vehicle Routing Problem

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Administrative information

Basic information on the SuCoLo project and this deliverable:

Project title	SuCoLo: Fostering sustainable consumer behaviour with inclusive bicycle logistics infrastructure in urban outskirts
Project coordinator	Salzburg Research Forschungsgesellschaft mbH (SRFG), Salzburg, Austria; project coordinator: Michael Thelen
Project partners	Independent L. ONLUS (IND), Italy Sustainability InnoCenter (SIC), Sweden VIABIRDS Technologies GmbH (VIA), Austria Universität Leipzig (ULEI), Germany Südtiroler Transportstrukturen AG – Green Mobility Department (STA), Italy
Funding	DUT Call 2022 – European Commission under the Horizon Europe Partnership scheme Funding is being provided by the Austrian Research Promotion Agency (FFG), Ministry of Enterprises and Made in Italy (MIMIT), the Federal Ministry of Research, Technology and Space in Germany (BMFTR), and the Swedish funding agency (Vinnova)
Project nr.	F-DUT-2022-0007
Duration	01/2024 – 06/2026
Website	https://sucolo.eu/
Deliverable nr.	D2.4
Deliverable title	Software prototype for routing and scheduling of delivery orders
Authors	Benjamin Gaunitz, Silvia Torres Landaverde, Viola Süß University of Leipzig, Logistics Living Lab
Version & status	Version 1.0
Date	12.08.2025

Purpose of the document

The purpose of this document is to present the development and functionality of a routing prototype built from open-source software and open data specifically designed for bicycle couriers, focusing on the operational aspects of the implementation of sustainable cargo bike logistics (T2.4 *Delivery scheduling and route optimisation for bicycle couriers*). The software routing prototype focuses on optimising delivery routes by considering vehicle-specific constraints of bicycle couriers, such as the extent of cycling infrastructure, accessibility, and courier capabilities. It aims to improve delivery efficiency, reduce travel distances, and support more effective route planning specifically tailored to bike-based logistics. This software prototype serves as a benchmark to compare route calculation with other courier software and to further refine it to answer the specific routing challenges faced when delivering via cargo bike (e.g., to prefer certain routes, avoid sharp turns / ways, consider time-windows, driver skills). In doing so, the aim is to demonstrate that open-source software and open data can be harnessed to solve unique routing problems for bike couriers or mixed fleet operators. This document outlines the conceptual approach, technical implementation and potential applications of the routing solution.

Executive Summary

The SuCoLo software prototype addresses the challenge of optimizing last-mile delivery for bicycle and mixed-fleet logistics by integrating route calculation, vehicle routing optimisation, visualisation, and containerized deployment. Its primary objective is to improve delivery efficiency, reduce travel distances, and support sustainable urban mobility solutions while considering specific contextual factors involved in biking. In doing so, this prototype directly contributes to SuCoLo WP2's goal of supporting bicycle and mixed-fleet delivery operators to optimise their delivery routing and scheduling of orders without the use of proprietary software: the SuCoLo software prototype is fully based on open-source software. The prototype's flexible and modular architecture allows for scalability and flexibility to adapt it to other purposes and contexts.

At its core, the prototype combines the Open Source Routing Machine (OSRM) to calculate travel times and distances with the Vehicle Routing Open-source Optimization Machine (VROOM) to assign tasks such as deliveries and pickups to vehicles in an efficient way, considering operational constraints like time windows, vehicle capacity, and load limits. The system processes structured input and produces optimized routes with timing and constraint-violation indicators.

A modular web frontend has been developed to demonstrate the integrated capabilities of OSRM and VROOM. It visualizes routing scenarios, showing task distribution across vehicles and corresponding routes. While the current demonstrator focuses on predefined scenarios, it lays the groundwork for future interactive planning and real-time optimization.

The technical infrastructure runs within a Rancher 1.6 container cluster, with APISIX acting as the API gateway, Let's Encrypt providing TLS-secured HTTPS, and Keycloak managing authentication and access control. Source code and automated deployments are managed via GitHub. The modular design enables flexible adaptation and the integration of additional features.

By leveraging open-source technologies and open data, the prototype demonstrates a reproducible, adaptable, and scalable approach to solving routing challenges in sustainable logistics. The next steps will focus on incorporating real delivery data and GPS tracks from a local cargo-bike courier in Leipzig to refine routing profiles, compare performance against existing software, and enhance operational relevance for logistics providers across Europe.

The prototypes discussed in this document and the source code thereof can be accessed here:

GitHub Repository	https://github.com/Logistics-Living-Lab/sucolo-routing-frontend	
Routing App	https://llhub.wifa.uni-leipzig.de:7800/sucolo-routing-app/	Credentials required
VROOM API	https://llhub.wifa.uni-leipzig.de:7800/vroom/	Credentials required

1. Background on the software prototype

Task 2.4 involves building a software prototype to specifically support bike-based deliveries in the SuCoLo project. The goal is to make order distribution more efficient by optimising delivery routes, automatically scheduling orders, and bundling multiple deliveries together. The software uses local data like road networks and traffic rules to plan the best routes and group orders that are close in time or location. This helps reduce delivery times, cut down on emissions, and make bike deliveries more practical and cost-effective in the city. Furthermore, the prototype is designed to be easily adapted for other cities with similar needs. Currently, the software solution is being evaluated in the Leipzig pilot area (Lützschena-Stahmeln), which will serve as a basis for future refinements.

2. Technological aspects

To carry this out, the prototype integrates three key technological components: Frontend App, VROOM, and OSRM (as shown in Figure 1):

Figure 1: Architecture of the software prototype

2.1.1 Open Source Routing Machine (OSRM)

OSRM (1) is a powerful tool used to calculate the fastest and most efficient routes between locations. It is built entirely on top of OpenStreetMap data, which is a free, crowd-sourced map of the world created and maintained by a global community of volunteers. This means OSRM does not rely on any proprietary or commercial mapping services; it uses open data that anyone can access, modify, and improve. At its core, OSRM reads and interprets the structure of roads, intersections, and pathways from OpenStreetMap (2) data. It understands how streets are connected, the rules of the road like one-way streets and turn restrictions, and even the type of surface a path has. With this information, it builds a model of the road network that allows it to quickly answer questions like “What’s the fastest way to get from here to there?” Whether the goal is to drive across a country, bike through a city, or walk around a neighbourhood, OSRM can provide accurate and realistic routes. One of OSRM’s biggest strengths is speed. It’s designed to handle very large maps and respond to route requests in milliseconds, which is crucial for real-time applications.

A delivery service that constantly updates directions or a fleet management system that recalculates optimized sequences can rely on OSRM to perform fast, complex routing tasks. Another important feature of OSRM is its flexibility. Because it is open source and self-hosted, users can fully customize how routes are calculated based on specific needs. This includes preferring or avoiding certain road types, excluding toll roads, or tuning routing behaviour for different travel modes like walking or cycling. In our solution, two separate OSRM instances are used - one configured for car routing and another for bike routing. This allows optimization and routing tasks to switch between different travel profiles depending on the use case, providing more accurate results for each transport mode.

2.1.2 Vehicle Routing Open-source Optimization Machine (VROOM)

Despite OSRM being utilized as the core routing engine, it is employed to compute fast and efficient point-to-point routes using OpenStreetMap data. While OSRM is highly effective for calculating individual routes and estimating travel times or distances, it does not provide built-in support for solving the complex logistical challenges that arise in real-world operations involving multiple stops and multiple vehicles.

To address these limitations, VROOM (3) is integrated on top of OSRM to perform advanced vehicle routing optimization. VROOM is designed specifically to solve a class of logistical problems known as vehicle routing problems (VRPs), which are central to the planning and execution of delivery services, field operations, passenger transport, and other fleet-based activities. These problems involve determining how a set of tasks - such as deliveries, pickups, or service visits - can be efficiently assigned to a fleet of vehicles. Each task must be scheduled in a way that minimises travel time or distance, while also respecting various operational constraints. These constraints may include time windows during which tasks must be completed, vehicle load capacities, maximum allowable driving times, start and end locations of vehicles, and required service durations at each stop.

VROOM is used to automatically compute optimised routes that take all of these factors into account. It determines not only the best sequence in which stops should be visited, but also how tasks should be distributed across the available vehicles to ensure an even and efficient workload. Support is also provided for different routing models, including roundtrips (where vehicles return to their starting point) and open-ended trips (where start and end points differ). The generated solutions are realistic and executable, reflecting the practical limitations and goals of day-to-day logistics. An overview of all supported API parameters is provided in Table 1, and a complete example of a routing request using vehicles and shipments within Leipzig, Germany is shown in Figure 2.

Table 1: VROOM API parameters

Category	Parameter	Name	Type
vehicles	id	integer	Unique vehicle identifier
vehicles	start	array [lon, lat]	Optional start location coordinates
vehicles	end	array [lon, lat]	Optional end location coordinates
vehicles	profile	string	Optional routing profile (e.g., car, bike)
vehicles	capacity	array [int]	Optional vehicle capacity for load dimensions
vehicles	time_window	array [int, int]	Optional operating time window [start, end] in seconds
vehicles	speed_factor	float	Optional scaling factor for travel time estimation
vehicles	skills	array [int]	Optional list of skill IDs required for jobs/shipments
vehicles	breaks	array [object]	Optional breaks with location and duration
vehicles	steps	bool	Optional, when true forces route steps in output
jobs	id	integer	Unique job identifier
jobs	location	array [lon, lat]	Required geographic coordinates
jobs	service	integer	Optional service duration at location in seconds
jobs	amount	array [int]	Optional load requirements
jobs	time_windows	array of [int, int]	Optional list of acceptable time windows
jobs	priority	integer	Optional priority (0–100, higher is more preferred)
jobs	skills	array [int]	Optional list of required skills
shipments	id	integer	Unique shipment ID
shipments.pickup	location	array [lon, lat]	Required pickup coordinates
shipments.pickup	service	integer	Optional pickup service time in seconds
shipments.pickup	amount	array [int]	Optional pickup load
shipments.pickup	time_windows	array of [int, int]	Optional pickup time windows
shipments.pickup	skills	array [int]	Optional required skills for pickup
shipments.delivery	location	array [lon, lat]	Required delivery coordinates
shipments.delivery	service	integer	Optional delivery service time in seconds
shipments.delivery	amount	array [int]	Optional delivery load
shipments.delivery	time_windows	array of [int, int]	Optional delivery time windows
shipments.delivery	skills	array [int]	Optional required skills for delivery
shipments	priority	integer	Optional shipment priority (0–100)
options	g	boolean	Include route geometry in response
options	c	boolean	Include ETA (computed start and arrival times)
options	t	integer	Number of threads used (default = hardware concurrency)
options	x	integer	Exploration level for optimization (default = 5)
options	l	integer	Timeout limit in milliseconds
options	sort	boolean	Sort jobs and shipments (default = false)
options	objective	string	Optional optimization goal (e.g., min-cost, balance)
input	geometry	string	Optional (polyline, geojson), output geometry format
input	format	string	Optional input format (for CLI/express server variants)

```

{
  // Vehicles define their start and end locations, profile, and optional constraints
  "vehicles": [
    {
      "id": 1,
      "profile": "car",           // Routing profile (matches OSRM profile)
      "start": [12.3731, 51.3397], // Leipzig city center (longitude, latitude)
      "end": [12.3731, 51.3397],  // Round trip: vehicle returns to start
      "capacity": [100],          // Max load (for shipments)
      "time_window": [0, 36000]   // Operates from time=0 to time=10h (36000 seconds)
    }
  ],

  // Shipments include both a pickup and a delivery job, linked together
  "shipments": [
    {
      "id": 101,
      "pickup": {
        "location": [12.3790, 51.3405], // Pickup near Leipzig Zoo
        "service": 300,                 // 5 min service time
        "amount": [20]                  // Load added to the vehicle
      },
      "delivery": {
        "location": [12.3984, 51.3322], // Delivery location in Leipzig east
        "service": 300,                 // 5 min unload time
        "amount": [20]                  // Load removed from the vehicle
      }
    }
  ],

  // Options customize the solution behavior
  "options": {
    "g": true,    // Include route geometry in the response
    "c": true     // Include ETA (calculated based on vehicle's time window and service times)
  }
}

```

Figure 2: VROOM Sample API Request

2.1.3 Frontend / Angular Web Application

To showcase the capabilities of the OSRM and VROOM integration, a frontend demonstrator application has been developed. Its main purpose is to visualise how routing and optimization processes work together in various logistical scenarios. Instead of offering full planning functionality, the application focuses on a set of predefined example cases that represent realistic transport situations involving multiple vehicles, jobs, and constraints. The frontend is built using Angular (5) and integrates Mapbox (6) for interactive map visualization. Users can explore the routing results directly on the map, including how tasks are assigned to vehicles and how routes are optimized based on constraints like time windows, capacities, and service durations. The application communicates with the VROOM API to request optimized solutions, and then renders the responses in real time, showing route geometries, arrival times, and vehicle-task assignments. This demonstrator serves as a technical tool to better understand how input parameters influence routing behavior. It provides insight into the structure of the optimization process by visualizing job distributions and route sequences in a clear and accessible way. While it is currently limited to predefined scenarios, the system is modular and prepared for future expansion. Planned improvements include support for custom input creation, constraint editing, and triggering new optimization runs directly from the user interface (UI). The combination of Angular, Mapbox, and VROOM API integration makes the application a practical foundation for building more advanced planning and dispatching tools in the future. The UI features are explained in Figures 3 and 4, as well as pre-defined scenarios in Table 2.

Figure 3: Routing app features

Figure 4: Calculated route on the routing app

Table 2: Settings - Pre-defined scenarios

Scenario	Start Depot	Deliver Shipment from Depot	Vehicle Capacity	Vehicles
Scenario 1 Deliver from Plagwitz Depot	FULMO Plagwitz Depot	yes	unlimited	1x Cargo bike
Scenario 2 Deliver from Micro-Hub	FULMO Lützschena Micro-Hub	yes	unlimited	1x Cargo bike
Scenario 3 PickUp & Deliver in Lützschena	FULMO Lützschena Micro-Hub	no	unlimited	1x Cargo bike
Scenario 4 Multiple Vehicles / Limited Capacity	FULMO Lützschena Micro-Hub	yes	max. 4 boxes	3x Cargo bike

2.1.4 Technical Infrastructure

The system is built on a containerized microservices architecture and deployed within a Rancher 1.6 cluster. Rancher (7) manages orchestration using Docker containers and providing centralized management of hosts, services, networking, and storage across multiple environments. This setup supports high availability and service isolation, with each component deployed as an independent containerized workload.

Source code management is handled through GitHub (8), which enables team-based collaboration through pull requests, branching strategies, and version tagging. GitHub also supports Continuous Integration and Deploy to enable automated build pipelines, continuous testing, and deployment to the Rancher-managed cluster.

Figure 5: GitHub repository (source: <https://github.com/Logistics-Living-Lab/sucolo-routing-frontend>)

External access to services is routed through APISIX (9), a high-performance, dynamic, and cloud-native API gateway. APISIX provides load balancing, traffic routing, rate limiting, retries, caching, and observability, and supports both REST and gRPC protocols. Incoming requests are authenticated and authorized at the gateway level, and routing rules can be dynamically reloaded without downtime. APISIX serves as the single-entry point for all external clients and is configured to expose only necessary services while hiding internal components.

To secure all client-server communication, HTTPS is enforced through Let's Encrypt (10), which is used to automatically provision and renew TLS certificates. Certificates are integrated automatically within the Rancher environment, ensuring encryption and data integrity across the system without manual intervention.

Authentication and authorization are centralized using Keycloak (11), an open-source identity and access management solution. Keycloak handles user login, identity federation (e.g., LDAP, OAuth2, SAML), and session management. It also supports role-based access control (RBAC), enabling granular permission settings across different user groups. Keycloak integrates seamlessly with the frontend and backend, issuing JWT tokens for stateless authentication and enforcing access policies in a standardized and scalable manner.

Depending on the deployment setup, additional infrastructure components may be used for service discovery, logging, and monitoring, such as Prometheus/Grafana, Fluentd, or ELK Stack, though these may vary by environment.

3. Conclusion and Outlook

The development of the SuCoLo routing and scheduling prototype aims to make a step towards enabling more efficient, sustainable and inclusive bicycle and mixed vehicle logistics. By leveraging open-source tools such as OSRM and VROOM, combined with a modular frontend demonstrator, its aim is to demonstrate that open-source software and open data can be used to solve unique routing problems for bike couriers or mixed fleet operators.

Looking ahead, the solution will be further refined with delivery data and GPS tracks retrieved from a local bicycle courier in Leipzig, with a focus on enhancing its accuracy and features. Specifically, the local bicycle courier will discuss the disadvantages of their current operational software, where it has already been identified that certain routings are not planned nor calculated for cargo bikes. Here, route calculations between the two solutions will be compared and serve as a benchmark for further iterations of the SuCoLo prototype. The SuCoLo prototype is fully flexible, where the routing algorithm can be adjusted (e.g., to prefer certain routes, avoid sharp turns / ways) or take into account specific vehicle or shipment limitations (e.g., time-windows, driver skills, size).

All in all, the objective of these developments is to support more dynamic planning and decision-making for last-mile logistics operators that possess bicycle fleets or mixed vehicle fleets, as well as to strengthen the role of sustainable delivery vehicles in urban mobility systems. By building upon existing open technologies and bringing them together, the SuCoLo software prototype lays the groundwork for a scalable, adaptable solution that can benefit cities and logistics providers across Europe.

References

- (1) Open Source Routing Machine. (n.d.). *OSRM – Open Source Routing Machine*. <https://project-osrm.org/>
- (2) OpenStreetMap. (n.d.). *OpenStreetMap*. <https://www.openstreetmap.org/>
- (3) VROOM Project. (n.d.). *VROOM*. <http://vroom-project.org/> ; VROOM Project. (n.d.). *VROOM GitHub repository*. <https://github.com/VROOM-Project>
- (4) Toth, P., & Vigo, D. (2002). *An overview of vehicle routing problems* (Chapter 1). In P. Toth & D. Vigo (Eds.), *The Vehicle Routing Problem* (pp. 1–26). SIAM Monographs on Discrete Mathematics and Applications. Society for Industrial and Applied Mathematics. <https://doi.org/10.1137/1.9780898718515.ch1>
- (5) Angular. (n.d.). *Angular*. <https://angular.dev/>
- (6) Mapbox. (n.d.). *Mapbox*. <https://www.mapbox.com/>
- (7) Rancher Labs. (n.d.). *Rancher 1.6 documentation*. <https://www.rancher.com/docs/rancher/v1.6/en/>
- (8) Logistics Living Lab. (n.d.). *SuCoLo routing frontend GitHub repository*. <https://github.com/Logistics-Living-Lab/sucolo-routing-frontend>
- (9) APISIX. (n.d.). *Apache APISIX gateway*. <https://apisix.apache.org/>
- (10) Let's Encrypt. (n.d.). *Let's Encrypt*. <https://letsencrypt.org/>
- (11) Keycloak. (n.d.). *Keycloak*. <https://www.keycloak.org/>